

en**vi**sion

D7.2 INTERMEDIATE REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Responsible Author	Ms. Aleksandra Kocet (ITC)		
Contributions from	Mr. Daniel Copot (ITC)		

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the ENVISION project is to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land and hence shift the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring.

This deliverable presents the review of the situation of dissemination and communication actions after the 18 months of ENVISION project implementation following the plan of activities as described in deliverable D7.1 Dissemination and Communication plan (M4).

The plan was the basis of widespread dissemination of the overall work and results of the project, during implementation, but also beyond the project's end. Based on the objectives of the strategy, the defined dissemination activities were aimed at enhancing public awareness and ensuring the involvement of targeted stakeholders in order to raise awareness of the objectives, activities and outcomes of the project.

Described dissemination and communication activities will be analysed in this deliverable.

1 Introduction

The main purpose of dissemination activities is to transfer knowledge and results generated within the project to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of the EU-funded research. Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the ENVISION targeted audiences is important to achieve a long-term impact and market-uptake of the project outcomes. All partners are requested to plan their dissemination activities and report their achievements as compared to their planned activities. For this purpose, the form on the Jotform has been prepared: <https://form.jotform.com/210193573145048>

This form helps all the partners for easy reporting and WP7 leader a clear view of dissemination and communication activities that have been done.

COVID-19 has dramatically reshaped our oral/face to face communication. Due to the current situation, no physical events were held between the project partners or external stakeholders.

The main project dissemination activities are presented in the following subchapters.

2 Dissemination and communication tools and activities

During the 18 months from the beginning of the project, ENVISION communication tools and promotional material were developed: templates, project leaflet, website and social media accounts. Two ENVISION Newsletters were issued, and the third one is in progress. The Kick-off event Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies and the ENVISION Advisory Board Kick-off meeting was organised. The communication actions are undertaken in those first months of the project generated a positive impact on the target audience.

2.1 ENVISION website

The main interface for communication with the public is the ENVISION website <https://envision-h2020.eu/>. The website has been running since the beginning of the project and is regularly updated by the webmaster with input from partners. The website also links to the ENVISION social media pages with an exposed tab to the side of the website.

Figure 1: The ENVISION project website

The main website features/sections are:

- Home: providing the main information about the project.

Benefits

Continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural practices
Farmers Support for Adhering to sustainable practices

ENVISION services address the following impacts stemming from unsustainable agricultural activities:

- Soil degradation
- Biodiversity loss
- Landscape degradation
- CHG emissions
- Water pollution

and support farmers towards compliance to different environmental and good agricultural practice rules.

Toolbox of services	Users
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web platform Mobile application Add-on development Tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies Farmers Third-Party developers

ENVISION mission

ENVISION aims to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land, shifting the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring. It will make use of heterogeneous types of available data and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies for providing a fully-automated and scalable toolbox of services, built in close interaction with its future customers.

[READ MORE ABOUT US](#)

Figure 2: The ENVISION home page

- About: providing more information about the project, data and products, services, business cases and target audience.

envision Home About News & Events Networking Deliverables Partners Newsletter Signup

About

Innovative

Continuous and systematic monitoring of 100% of farmers through Earth observation

Reliable

Use of heterogeneous types of available data and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies.

envision Home About News & Events Networking Deliverables Partners Newsletter Signup

Description

ENVISION contributes in the achievement of CAP's environmental objectives, offering the tools for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability. These tools reinforce the monitoring of environmental- and climate-friendly agricultural practices stemming from EU policy ensuring that the agricultural activities do not severely impact the climate and nature.

Data and Data Products

ENVISION fully exploits the wealth of data made available through GEOS and Copernicus and its synergetic use with other data to develop data products such as: Cultivated crop type maps; Soil Organic Carbon; Distinction of organic – conventional farming; Grassland mowing/ploughing; Soil erosion.

It makes use of heterogeneous types of available data (EO-based, in situ, open data, and historical on-field check data) and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies (automatic pixel/texture/object oriented change detection and classification methods, machine learning, data fusion, multi-source and multi-temporal data management) for providing a fully-automated and scalable toolbox of services, built in close interaction with its future customers.

envision Home About News & Events Networking Deliverables Partners Newsletter Signup

Services

The toolbox of services addresses existing gaps in compliance and monitoring processes of agri-environmental and climate rules for CAP post-2020 era while facilitating farmers towards more sustainable agricultural practices. Therefore, the ENVISION toolbox is a concrete set of tools that PAs & CBs can provide to farmers for adhering to environmentally friendly agricultural practices, as well as an Add-on Development Tool that can be used by third-party developers to extent ENVISION functionality. The ENVISION monitoring service identifies unsustainable agriculture practices that can result to the following interrelated environmental impacts: Soil degradation; Biodiversity loss; Landscape degradation; GHG emissions; Water pollution.

Business Cases

ENVISION develops services that best fit the needs of PAs and OCBs helping them to master the complex processes of monitoring farmers' performance in relation to the environmental rules stemming from EU policy. These services will be tested and validated in an operational environment not only by the project pilot partners but also by a group of Lighthouse Customers. A market analysis, business model experimentation techniques and appropriate decision-making tools will determine the commercially viable business models for the services and products of ENVISION, and define alternative business models, understand their implications and identify those that will create the greatest value.

Figure 3: The ENVISION about page

- News & Events: contains recent news, published newsletters, events and media hub.

Figure 4: The ENVISION News & Events page

- Networking: ENVISION is networking with other projects related to Earth Observation, listed under this tab.

Figure 5: The ENVISION Networking page

- Deliverables: Public deliverables are uploaded and marked in green.

Figure 6: The ENVISION Deliverables page

- Partners: All project partners are listed with their logos. When you click on their logo, the link leads you to their website.

Figure 7: The ENVISION Partners page

- Newsletter Signup: signup form for the project’s newsletter

Figure 8: The ENVISION Newsletter Signup page

You find the disclaimer, EU logo, and contact details on every section bottom.

Figure 9: The ENVISION contacts details

The Privacy Policy and the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the ENVISION website, which is a set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

2.2 Social Media

To reach a broad target audience, the use of social media is essential. A strong social media presence is helping ENVISION to reach a broader audience, especially stakeholders who are difficult to reach through direct personal interaction.

ENVISION LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook are active from the beginning of the project - September 2020, YouTube from June 2021, and SlideShare from January 2022. WP7 leader is responsible for keeping them updated, and every project partner is asked to send news and relevant information to the WP7 leader. An image accompanies posts as this delivers stronger engagement levels.

The hashtags being used are the following:

[#earthobservation](#) [#agriculture](#) [#sustainable](#) [#environmental](#) [#monitoringsystem](#) [#payingagency](#) [#co designing](#) [#cocreation](#) [#farms](#) [#farming](#) [#agritech](#) [#innovation](#) [#certifications](#) [#certifyingbodis](#).

Table 1: Social Media Channels

Social Media Channel	Direct Link
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC7a4V9GgwQhPAneqnmqmsxQ
SlideShare	https://www.slideshare.net/EnvisionH2020

2.2.1 ENVISION LinkedIn page

LinkedIn offers an opportunity to connect with concrete and growing user base. Therefore, the target audience is sector-specific such as technical groups, researchers and academia, and professional associations.

Figure 10: The ENVISION LinkedIn page

LinkedIn is more formal in nature, so the posts are longer and use language more relevant to the ENVISION project.

Figure 11: ENVISION LinkedIn post example

2.2.2 ENVISION Twitter page

Twitter offers an ideal platform to connect with all target audiences – the wider public and the professional community. The main objective is to build a range of followers interested in the agri-tech space and the ENVISION project. This will enable communication and dissemination of the project activities.

Figure 12: The ENVISION Twitter page

Posts are concise due to the nature of the Twitter platform.

Figure 13: ENVISION Tweet example

2.2.3 ENVISION Facebook page

Facebook targets both professional and individual users, effectively builds relationships and shows the human side of the ENVISION project, i.e. the partners, the events and presentations being attended, and the marketing materials produced.

Figure 14: The ENVISION Facebook page

The content is more relaxed than Twitter and LinkedIn, and overly scientific language is avoided.

Figure 15: ENVISION Facebook post example

2.2.4 ENVISION YouTube channel

The ENVISION Youtube channel was created in the summer of 2021. The ENVISION introduction video was filmed. The project partners had to in 30 seconds present their organisation (visibility of the team) and what they would produce (tangible outcomes). The decision was to record a less formal video, recorded outside in nature. Up to now, the ENVISION Youtube channel has 20 subscribers, besides the introduction video, four videos from the project partners and the recording from the clustering event named Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy are also included.

Figure 16: ENVISION YouTube channel

2.2.5 ENVISION SlideShare

The last channel of the social media that was opened was the ENVISION Slideshare. This channel will be used to share presentation slides. At this moment, the first published presentation is the overview of the ENVISION project.

Figure 17: ENVISION Slideshare

2.3 ENVISION e-Newsletters

The newsletters are created through MailChimp, a web-based e-mail marketing service. They are distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a signup form on the website. ENVISION e-Newsletters are released every six months, offering the project community with an overview of the latest project activities and developments. e-Newsletters are uploaded on the project website, distributed to a list of recipients and published in social media channels.

Partners may also promote the newsletter through their channels. An unsubscribe/opt-out link is available as per EU directive 2002/58/EC. Contributions are sought from all partners and particularly WP leaders.

The first edition of the newsletter was released in February 2021, announcing the start of the project; the Project Coordinator presented the first six months of the project and the invitation for agricultural Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies to take part in the online survey to help ENVISION projects partners understand what kind of earth observation services might be useful for their organisation in the area of monitoring agricultural practices.

Figure 18: ENVISION Newsletter #1

The second edition of the newsletter was released in September 2021. This edition announced the first version of the ENVISION platform and presented the ENVISION business cases where the services will be tested and validated in an operational environment by the project pilot's partners.

Figure 19: ENVISION Newsletter #2

The third edition of the newsletter is in preparation and will be issued at the beginning of March.

2.4 ENVISION promotional material

Diverse types of promotional material were designed for print, and are also available in digital form on the project website. Partners are invited to share this promotional material on suitable occasions, thus putting ENVISION directly in the hands of the right set of the target audience.

These include:

- Roll-up and poster
- Leaflet
- Templates for PowerPoint presentations
- Deliverable templates

Figure 20: ENVISION poster

Figure 21: ENVISION roll-up

Figure 22: PowerPoint template

Figure 23: Deliverable template

2.5 Meetings with developers, open-source communities

Ten meetings with developers and open-source communities were planned. Meetings that have already been organised and their content are provided in the table below.

Table 2: Meetings with developers, open-source communities

Project Partner	Date	Developers	Meeting description
ITC	3/2/2021	AGRIVI	The introductory event has been organised between ITC and Agrivi to provide services to farmers using EO data.

Project Partner	Date	Developers	Meeting description
			Agrivi is one of the leading developers of the Farm management system, with EO as one of the important sources of information for farmers. ITC presented ENVISION project and its future services, while Agrivi presented their platform and view on the digital transformation of the agrifood sector.
NOA	2/7/2021	Sen4Cap	A more dedicated, technical discussion on Sen4CAP with respect to deployment, algorithms or other technical related issues.
ITC	12/8/2021	Sinergise	The meeting between ITC and Sinergise (Sentinel hub partner and organisation providing open source EO services), with the following agenda: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short presentation of both organisations - Presentation of the ENVISION project, Farm manager platform and services to be used - Sinergise (Mr Grega Milčinski) to be involved in ENVISION as an Advisory Board member - Follow up meeting in October 2021
NPA	23/9/2021	Agricultural exhibition "Kā pasēsi..."	Agricultural exhibition "Kā pasēsi..." is held since 1996. It is the largest exhibition for agro-industry innovations in the Baltic States. Policy makers also visited the NPA exhibition stand and were interested in general workflow and how monitoring data could be used as a prevention tool. Around 120 people visited the NPA exhibition stand.
ITC	14/10/2021	Sinergise	The meeting at Sinergise had the following agenda: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farm manager and integration of Sinergise/ENVISION services in the platform for advisors and farmers - AB member and Sinergise/ITC activities in the ENVISION, Sen4CAP, NIVA4CAP, cross-fertilisation - Other collaboration activities
AgroApps	12/1/2022	GitLab Inc	AgroApps approached Christos Bacharakis from GitLab Inc in order to include him in the AB since he is an active member of the open-source dev community. They presented him the project and the progress performed up to now.

2.6 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

On-site visits to targeted potential customers and meetings with stakeholders at national and EU level were planned. These meetings are held beyond the project events aiming at presenting ENVISION's results and activities at different stages of the project development. Due to the COVID situation, they take place online.

Table 3: Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
ITC	10/9/2020	The University of Maribor, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science KGZS MS Institute of Agriculture and Forestry Murska Sobota Skylabs Inova IT	ITC organised a meeting with relevant stakeholders. The main topic of the discussion was the economics of farming with the support of geospatial analysis. Besides the presentations of all the projects, ITC and KGZS MS presented the current state of the art: measurement parameters, technique, measurement, the influence of measurement elements on production. Skylabs and Inova IT presented their products.
ITC	11/2/2021	Agricultural Chamber – Institute Murska Sobota	The goal of the meeting was to present ENVISION project and future services that can be potentially implemented in the Farm manager service developed jointly by ITC and the Agricultural Chamber.
AgroApps	3/5/2021	OPEKEPE	Informal discussion with the PA of Greece (OPEKEPE) in order to be involved in the project as an LHC.
ETAM	10/5/2021	EO4AGRI project	Participants: Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM SA), Ifigeneia Tsioutsia (Agroapps), Jason Tsardanidis, Alexandros Marantos, Vasileios Sitokonstantinou, Thanasis Drivas (NOA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.3 of EO4AGRI • Regarding the list of potential collaborations, he proposed adding the theme of standardisation.
ETAM	13/5/2021	VITIGEOSS project	Meeting with VITIGEOSS project, representative Rosa Maria Araujo Rivero. Participants: Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM SA), Ifigeneia Tsioutsia (Agroapps), Jason Tsardanidis, Alexandros Marantos, Vasileios Sitokonstantinou, Manos Lekakis (Agroapps).

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
ETAM	17/5/2021	FIRE project	Meeting with FIREproject, representative Natassa Antoniou, Martin Utray, Christopher Oligschlager Participants: Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM SA), Ifigeneia Tsioutsia (AgroApps), Jason Tsardanidis, Alexandros Marantos (NOA).
ETAM	24/5/2021	EUROPABON project	Meeting with EUROPABON project, representative Jessica Junker, Ian Macallum Participants: Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM SA), Ifigeneia Tsioutsia (AgroApps), Jason Tsardanidis, Alexandros Marantos, Vasileios Sitokonstantinou (NOA)
ETAM	30/5/2021	NIVA project	ENVISION meeting with NIVA project, Dr Sander Janssen and Eva DeJonge. ENVISION got an invitation from them to see their open outputs, code source and tools, and provide them information regarding our open outputs. They will organise new webinars after summer and ENVISION was encouraged to take part. NIVA has a tool called “Technology watchdog” (internal publication for technology), and they asked ENVISION to provide a use case. Lastly, NIVA proposed a joint webinar together with all relevant projects (e.g. SEN4CAP, NIVA, ENVISION etc).
AgroApps	4/6/2021	Strutt & Parker	An informal discussion with a previous partner of the RECAP project, Jason Beedell, an Agricultural consultant from Strutt & Parker, a trading style of BNP Paribas Real Estate Advisory & Property Management UK Limited, asked him to join the AB. He said yes!!
ETAM	4/6/2021	MEF4CAP project	Meeting with MEF4CAP, representatives Nikolaos Kalatzis, Sokratis Skarpelis, Hans Vrolijk, Alberto Gutierrez. Participants: Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM SA), Ifigeneia Tsioutsia (AgroApps), Jason

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			Tsardanidis, Alexandros Marantos, Thanasis Drivas, Vasilis Sitokonstantinou (NOA)
ETAM	17/6/2021	SEN4CAP project	<p>Meeting with SEN4CAP project, Mr Pierre Fourny and Ms Sophie Bontemps: SEN4CAP has been formally closed last March. Nevertheless, they continue the support to the users. Their team commented about their collaboration with the NIVA project. Moreover, they briefed the ENVISION team about their final events in March, the new webinars planned for July and September, and they mentioned the availability of plenty of information on their website.</p> <p>Regarding ENVISION, they asked about the business cases and how exactly they are defined. Another question concerned how ENVISION plans to build upon other projects and if ENVISION has started from scratch. Also, they raised a question regarding the user requirements and the specificities of very small countries. ENVISION proposed a meeting between technical teams of the two projects and the organisation of a webinar and a joint publication. The SEN4CAP team said they are ready to provide their feedback on what ENVISION would like to report. ENVISION mentioned the problem faced regarding the download of images that are archived and relevant to this; an online meeting at the end of June was agreed to discuss how they can provide help. SEN4CAP proposed to the ENVISION team to submit questions on the SEN4CAP forum as they are still maintaining it, as well as they stressed that they are willing to discuss any win-win collaboration. The last topic of discussion was the availability and speed of responses of ESA to requests.</p>
ETAM	12/7/2021	VITIGEOSS	Following the first discussion with VITIGEOSS, ENVISION proposed a new meeting in order to explore the possibility

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			of building together a new business case for vineyards.
ETAM	14/9/2021	NIVA	Exchange of information regarding both projects. Invitation to RVO to become ENVISION Lighthouse customer. ENVISION proposal for a joint organisation of the event. Means for pushing Lighthouse customers' (stakeholders) engagement is of common interest. A new meeting will take place at some point during October. Early December is a good time for an event given the ENVISION planned progress. Encouragement to provide input to the "watchdog" tool of NIVA.
ITC	23/11/2021	NIVA	The draft agenda for the common event was reviewed: defined the involved projects, moderator and speakers. The event will be held on February 9th, 2022. ITC is responsible for the technical background and ZOOM.

2.7 Project events (seminars/workshops)

According to the project plan, dissemination and communication activities are a collaborative effort; therefore, every partner shall organise an event/seminar/workshop and actively participate in events organised by other partners. Consequently, at least 12 international events will be organised, presenting and demonstrating project outcomes and use-cases, while some of those events will have a policy and cross-fertilisation focus. Guidelines for managing the ENVISION events were prepared.

The team of AgriHUB of the BEYOND Center of Excellence (NOA) organised an online seminar to present their work regarding EO and AI for sustainable agriculture. The seminar was held on February 2, 2021. The audience was researchers from different sectors, e.g. Fire, floods, earthquakes etc.

Figure 24: Beyond Seminars – AgriHUB

OCS participated in the 1st Organic Fest of Srpska on September 24 and 25, 2021 in Banja Luka. OCS with InoSens held an ENVISION session at the festival – IT sector as a tool for the development of organic agriculture. They presented the project to certification bodies and paying agencies from the Balkans (Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia).

After the presentation, participants had an active discussion about the expectation from ENVISION project and the general IT sector. Lighthouse customers saw ENVISION as a big opportunity in controlling wide and more precise territory in organic plant production. Farmers concluded that this project is very interested in group certification when one or two internal auditors control more farmers.

Figure 25: ENVISION session – IT sector as a tool for the development of organic agriculture

ITC delivered the third event. The Kick-off event Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies was held on November 17, 2021. The kick-off event aimed to showcase the ENVISION innovative tools that are being developed for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability, in compliance with the CAPS agri-environmental objectives. Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies have shown interest in the tools that ENVISION is developing. Therefore, meetings with each of them will be organised in the future.

Figure 26: Kick-off meeting Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies

2.8 Clustering events/workshops

A clustering event named “Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy” was organised on February 9th, 2022. The event aimed to connect and explore future collaboration possibilities of European projects (NIVA, e-shape, DIONE, BEACON, EO-WIDGET) dealing with Earth Observation technologies for monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability, in compliance with the CAPs agri-environmental objectives, while further enhancing their visibility.

The event had showcased plenty of tangible outcomes/innovations and close collaboration among projects and organisations from both sides of the coin – research/service provision side and target user side (PAs, CBs and other stakeholders).

The final number of registered was 390. The recording and presentations are available on the ENVISION website:

<https://envision-h2020.eu/earth-observation-services-in-support-of-agriculture-and-common-agricultural-policy/>

Figure 27: Clustering event “Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy”

2.9 External events

The project partners attend external events (industry fairs, conferences and meetings) to present ENVISION, its activities and results. The table of indicative relevant events was prepared in the beginning, and it is updated regularly with the appropriate events.

The table below shows the events project partners attended.

Table 4: External events attended by ENVISION projects partners

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
OCS	14/10/2020	Presentation of the sign of organic products in the Republic of Srpska (an entity of Bosnia and Herzegovina)	Within the presentation of the label of organic products in the Republic of Srpska (an entity of Bosnia and Herzegovina) by the Ministry of Agriculture, organic production in this region was presented, as well as the growing importance of information technologies in agriculture. The General Manager of OCS (Nenad Novakovic) presented information about organic production in this area and also represented the ENVISION project. OCS presented the project to the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Srpska and

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			organic producers. Conclusions regarding ENVISION were that responsible people in the Republic of Srpska desire to be included in this project with information about parcels, crops, and other relevant information.
OCS	4/11/2020	Interview on television	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nUXDmFGxOxc&t=697s
ITC	15/11/2021	The WG Innovation ecosystems monthly teleconference	ITC / DIH AGRIFOOD has become a member of the AIOTI network, specifically involved in: WG 02 Smart Farming: the WG focused in identifying digital solutions that are supporting digital transformation in agrifood sector. The WG will be important to present ENVISION services and address target groups/potential new customers. WG 06 Innovation Ecosystems: the WG focused on networking cross-fertilisation of innovations, projects and networks. This WG will be used for ENVISION dissemination and exploitation activities and cross-fertilisation of ENVISION with other similar EU projects.
CAPO	9/3/2021	Copernicus and the Common Agricultural Policy	The event/meeting was an online workshop about the activities, operational and research, that have been developed to support the Common Agricultural Policy using Copernicus infrastructure, data or services. The workshop was relevant to Envision project goals and area of application. Many of the participants belonged to the business target group of the project. Also, EU officials responsible for forming the new CAP on a more technical level presented or expressed their views on future developments.
DRXS	16/4/2021	E-Shape co-design workshop	The workshop was very relevant and useful to DRXS work. It is important to understand the codesign challenges that other projects face and discuss ways to overcome them. ENVISION will be building on this workshop primarily by establishing more frequent communications/meetings with the eShape co-design team and other

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			projects (i.e., SAFERS adopts a very similar approach to ENVISION), to share experiences and receive feedback as the co-production process progresses.
URDG	16/4/2021	Workshop on European platforms & co-design best practices, e-shape and projects from topic H2020-SC5-16	Zoom meeting with representatives of the eShape, SAFERS, FIRE, ENVISION, NextLand, Vitigeoss, and SusTunTech projects. The primary aim of the meeting was to share experiences and progress relevant to the co-production/co-design process that each project adopts. Further meetings were arranged with the eShape co-design team to discuss the progress of ENVISION co-design on a frequent basis.
ITC	8/9/2021	Public advisory service Expert group workshop	The event was dedicated to present and explore digitalisation opportunities in agriculture. At the meeting, all regional advisors from Pomurje were present. The event will be followed by further implementation of ENVISION and new outcomes will be presented, when available, to the interested advisory service personnel - acting as LC in Slovenia.
OCS and INOS	25/9/2021	1st organic fest in the Republic of Srpska	1st organic fest in the Republic of Srpska opened by Ministry of agriculture. Organic products had been exposed on stands. Organic products of Serbia was on two stands, and on those stands ENVISION leaflet, poster and roll up had exposed. OCS and INOSENS presented the project to the visitors.
INOS	25/11/2021	DIONE Workshop SMART agricultural monitoring within the CAP umbrella and beyond	The DIONE workshop SMART agricultural monitoring within the CAP umbrella and beyond took place on the 25th of November with the intent to show and promote the DIONE Toolbox – a ready-to-market solution and unique fusion of innovative technologies in the service of improved agricultural monitoring. The workshop brought together Paying Agencies, Certification Bodies, Agricultural Consultants, Officials from Ministries to abide by the modernised CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) and other agri-related

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			regulations as well as for EO industry players to explore the DIONE business offering.
NOA	16/12/2021	AGU Fall meeting	At the AGU Fall meeting, Jason Tsardanidis from the ENVISION project partner NOA presented grassland mowing detection using deep learning architecture.

2.10 Presentations/attending at International Conferences

The partners attended the International Conferences:

Table 5: Presentations/attending at International Conferences

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
NOA	27/5/2021	Data Week	Data Week is the spring gathering of the European Big Data Value and Industrial AI research and innovation community. The event follows the tradition of the Big Data Value Summit, promoting opportunities, knowledge sharing and fostering ecosystem development.
NOA	27/5/2021	Data Week: REGAIN Workshop	REGAIN aims to offer an exciting and live workshop to put BDVA/DAIRO and EU community at large at the centre of emerging ecosystems. REGAIN collaborating networks and stakeholders foster the exchange of experience and fresh and breakthrough ideas, mostly linked with the “Ecosystem” track, aiming to widen and open Big Data/AI and Green Technologies/Circular Economy communities. NOA’s presentation: Big Earth Observations and Artificial Intelligence for Food Security Monitoring
NOA	23/6/2021	The Irish Organisation for Geographic Information (IRLOGI) – e-shape Workshop	NOA’s presentation: Agrowth: Phenology & Yield estimation to enhance farm performance.
NOA	13/7/2021	IGARSS 2021	The IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society and the IGARSS 2021 Organizing Committee invited NOA to the 41st annual IGARSS symposium. NOAs presentation: SEMI-SUPERVISED PHENOLOGY

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
			ESTIMATION IN COTTON PARCELS WITH SENTINEL-2 TIME-SERIES; TU2.MM – 25.8 Machine Learning Methods in Hazard Assessment
NPA	28/8/2021	Exhibition Inno panorama 2021	<p>The main focus of exhibition “Inno panorama” is digital technologies in agriculture and forestry. The audience comprises farmers, farmers associations, agriculture consultants, SME/innovators, policy makers, general public. During the exhibition, a conference “Solutions for Regional Development” was held with one of the main topics being Digitalization in Agriculture. Business, science, and government representatives shared their experience implementing digital methods and presented the Rural Development Programme opportunities for innovative solutions. Together with the exhibition, drone competitions were held by the Public Institution Rural Business and Market Development Agency.</p> <p>Moreover, during the event, the visitors observed the presentation of equipment, demonstration of possibilities for the use of data from drones in agriculture and enjoyed the interactive educational programme for the youth.</p>
URDG	21/9/2021	Symposium on Agri Tech Economics for Sustainable Futures	Introduced the co-production approach and importance of conversations between stakeholders to lead to a greater understanding when developing agri-tech.
OCS	24/9/2021	Organic production is an opportunity for the region, yes or no?”	Participants are representatives of the institutions (secretaries of Chambers and Ministry of agriculture and certification bodies) of the Republic of Srpska, Republic of Serbia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and organic producers. The debate was about opportunities in the common business of participating in the European market, focusing on practice in the European Union (Croatia).

2.11 PR articles published in national/regional/European press

PR articles published in national/regional/European press are important dissemination channels for sharing ENVISION results in the community.

Table 6: PR articles published in national/regional/European press

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
INOS	11/02/2021	Ecological interviews during COVID-19 pandemic	EkoNec	https://ekonec.wordpress.com/2021/02/11/ekoloski-intervju-u-doba-korone-vladimir-mrkajic-doktorinzenjerstva-zastite-zivotne-sredine-rukovodilacsektora-za-istrazivanje-i-razvoj-u-inosens-d-o-onista-nije-sveto-sve-je-bruto/ https://envision-h2020.eu/earth-observation-services-in-support-of-agriculture-and-common-agricultural-policy/
OCS	12/5/2021	Conference with advisors for organic products	SU Television	Reportage from the conference for advisors from Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) for organic production organised by OCS.
OCS	12/5/2021	Dnevnik RS	Dnevnik RS	https://www.dnevnik.rs/novi-sad/novi-sad-primerdobre-prakse-u-organskoj-proizvodni-13-05-2021?fbclid=IwAR2pzxQkzJaNb1fGVe-6NHIPfv4pKeWZksxijWo5kQNWlp69tdlZINfQin8
LEAF	1/12/2021	Farmer Engagement Survey	LEAF EBrief	Invitation to the LEAF network of farmers to complete the Farmer Engagement Survey being undertaken by Reading University. – This is a member only access.
ITC	8/12/2021	Financing the development and innovation in the agrifood sector	Finance	https://agrobiznis.finance.si/8983791/Kako-do-denarja-za-razvoj-in-inovacije-v-kmetijstvu-in-zivilski-industriji
LEAF	20/12/2021	LEAF Network Innovation News	LEAF Network Innovation News	https://issuu.com/linking-environment-andfarming/docs/nin_december_2021
ITC	12/2/2022	ENVISION PR#1		https://envision-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/ENVISION_P_R1_16.2.2022.pdf

2.12 Publications in business journals

NOA published its first publication in business journals:

- Title of the publication: “A Scalable Machine Learning Pipeline for Paddy Rice Classification Using Multi-Temporal Sentinel Data”,
- Authors: Sitokonstantinou, V.; Koukos, A.; Drivas, T.; Kontoes, C; Papoutsis, I.; Karathanassi
- Title of the Journal: Remote Sensing Volume 13 Issue 9
- Publication document (URL): <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/13/9/1769>

2.13 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

All partners focus on building up trust and cooperation with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions. Among other actions, we are arranging meetings to introduce the project initially. We will keep this constant relationship alive throughout the lifespan of the whole project.

Table 7: Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
ETAM	10/9/2020	Greek Inspection and Certification Organisation “TÜV HELLAS” (TUV Nord)	“TÜV HELLAS” (TUV Nord) is one of the Lighthouse Customers. Informative meeting with George Nikolaou & Uxue Azpiroz Lasarte on ENVISION’s kick start and request to fill out the UoR questionnaire.
NPA	11/2/2021	The European Parliament office in Lithuania, AgriFood DIH Lithuania	The online event “Digitalisation – an opportunity for agri-food sector” was the first event in the series of discussions, that will be organised on a monthly basis. Among the speakers of the event there were high-ranking Lithuanian officials. The scope of the debates comprised the overview of digitalisation achievements, challenges and aspirations of Lithuanian and European agricultural sector’ players. The focus was on possible assistance and consultancies for farmers as regards promotion of using innovative technologies in their agricultural practices.
OCS	24/2/2021	Presentation of the IT platform	Presentation of an IT platform that manufacturers can use, which will greatly simplify document management systems and thus control and speed up the certification of their own

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			production. The meeting was attended by representatives of the government of Serbia, the Serbian Chamber of Commerce, Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) and organic producers.
OCS	24/2/2021	Subvention in organic production intended for producers from Vojvodina (Provincial of Serbia)	General Manager of OCS (Nenad Novakovic) represented information about ENVISION project to the participants. The IT solutions (like offered by Envision), represent a new serious challenge in tracking potential environmental problems in agriculture.
NPA	4/3/2021	Sen4CAP Final User Workshop	<p>Success stories and lessons learned from Sen4Cap pilot countries. Uptake by external users.</p> <p>Technical presentations about the system and processors. Martynas Rimgaila delivered a presentation “Experience with Sen4CAP in Lithuania”. Presentations covered the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • specification of EO products and services suitable to increase the efficiency, traceability as well as reducing the costs of the IACS, • developing Algorithm Theoretical Basis Documents along with open source code for agricultural EO products based on Sentinel-1 & -2 responding to the user requirements, • demonstrating and validating the developed agricultural EO products up to national scale.
OCS	5/3/2021	Documentation keeping in organic production	Keeping records (documentation, plant growth, fertilizers, weather conditions, etc) of agricultural production through information technology, to facilitate monitoring of organic production by farmers, but also by the certification body.
NPA	9/3/2021	Baltic region workshop on use of area monitoring for checking conditionality	Discussion topics: Requirements relevant for area monitoring. Plans for sanctioning non-compliance determined by monitoring in comparison to sanctions based on non-compliance found by classical on-the-spot checks.

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			<p>Intentions to apply lower percentage reductions and approach.</p> <p>Sharing experience on use of area monitoring for checking conditionality and planning further online discussions.</p>
NPA	13/3/2021	Using satellite monitoring as a tool for conditionality	<p>Workshop on using satellite monitoring as a tool for conditionality, organised by the Danish Ministry of Agriculture and Paying Agency. Topics of presentations and discussions: Current state of CbM piloting.</p> <p>Cross-compliance. October 2020 survey results. New technologies for CC OTSC: 1) Farm sustainability tool for nutrients (FaST); 2) Future of CC – conditionality</p> <p>Aušrius Kučinskas from NPA delivered a presentation “Future CAP in Lithuania”. Participants – representatives of the Baltic- Nordic agricultural ministries and paying agencies.</p>
URDG	23/4/2021	Co-design self diagnosis with eShape’s co-design team	<p>Virtual meeting between the ENVISION and eShape co-design teams. The purpose of the meeting was a diagnosis of the co-design process that is being followed in ENVISION, and a thorough discussion about potential solutions to challenges identified thus far.</p>
NPA	7/4/2021	Panta Rhei workshop: Current status of the CbM	<p>Slovenia, acting as Panta Rhei Secretariat, on 7 April 2021 hosted an online workshop on the current status of the CbM. Slovenia presented its experience and problems encountered during the implementation of CbM.</p>
OCS	28/4/2021	Certification to success – Organic production	<p>Achieving success through organic certification procedures for organic certification in BiH, competent ministries and support measures, USAID project, examples and experience of organic certification in Serbia, Croatia and BiH. General manager of OCS Nenad Novakovic presented examples and experience of organic certification in Serbia and presented what is ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from project like this.</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
ITC	4/5/2021	Meeting with the Ministry of Agriculture, forestry and food	The meeting with the Slovenian Ministry and public advisory service (Chamber of Agriculture) took place in order to explore possibilities of sharing data and upgrading the Farm management platform, where ENVISION services could be offered to Slovenian target groups.
OCS	12/5/2021	Conference with advisors for organic products	Achieving success through organic certification, procedures for organic certification in BiH, examples and experience of organic certification in Serbia and BiH, presented ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from projects like this.
NPA	9/6/2021	49 Conference of Directors of EU Paying Agencies	Presentations, delivered by the EC representatives, included those on CAP reform negotiations, on latest developments as regards IACS (including LPIS and monitoring), on developments related to assurance and audit including the Annual Activity Report of DG AGRI.
EV ILVO	30/6/2021	ENVISION - United experts meeting	The meeting took place under the proposal and coordination of ILVO, inviting the United experts team from Belgium for a potential collaboration as a Lighthouse customer. From the ENVISION side, ILVO, URDG, AgroApps and ITC were present at the meeting. United experts are a consultancy company, providing legal and admin support for agricultural companies, working in the field of EO and other topics. They have established a strong collaboration with ILVO and would be interested to take part in the Use-case driven by ILVO in Belgium.
AgroApps	2/7/2021	Meeting with Jason Beedell	The meeting was organized between Agroapps, ITC and Jason Beedell, Director of Strutt & Parker / BNP Paribas Real Estate for a potential role in ENVISION project. Jason was involved in the RECAP project, which is a very good starting point, since he is familiar with the environment and content of both

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			projects. Ifigeneia and Daniel presented the project ENVISION; after that, we have discussed collaboration opportunities and Jason's role as Advisory Board member.
ETAM	8/7/2021	Meeting with the project SAFERS	The meeting was scheduled in order to exchange information about ENVISION and SAFERS, while exploring collaboration possibilities. The meeting was attended by: AGroApps, ETAM, NOA, ITC, SAFERS dissemination and communication lead (Maha AL-SALEHI). - ENVISION presented the field of operation and focus in agricultural monitoring - SAFERS is covering the issue of wild_res around Europe and globally. The project will create a platform, using different data sources (EO, in-situ, other sources) and supported by AI and producing different DSS type of information. They will have 4 demo sites (Italy, France, Greece, Spain).
URDG	26/7/2021	Meeting with Certification Bodies organised by LEAF	On July 26, 2021, URDG participated in the LEAF Certification Body Annual Meeting 2021, where presenting ENVISION, their role as an ENVISION partner and briefly discussed the potential for Certification Bodies to get involved in ENVISION as lighthouse customers. The meeting was organised by LEAF and URDG participated as an external associate. The primary aim of the meeting was the update, sharing of developments and concerns of Certification Bodies in the context of the LEAF Marque.
INOS	12/8/2021	Meeting with OCS Team	The discussion focused on opportunities to disseminate early project results at the First Organic Festival in Banja Luka.
NPA	14/9/2021	Sen4CAP 8th Workshop	Dominique Laurent, from IGN-France, presented their work achieved within the NIVA project on 2 topics strongly linked with the new CAP monitoring system: satellite (Sentinel) imagery

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			<p>access and an UML model on EO monitoring;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tor Nielsen, from Planet, spoke about the Planet data and their potential for CbM and introduced their work with pilot Paying Agencies in testing these Planet images. <p>Version 3.0 of the Sen4CAP system as well as information about the extension of the Sen4CAP activities, comprising new use cases, by launching a new ESA call in October 2021, was presented.</p>
NPA	17/9/2021	Conference of Baltic States - Polish Paying Agencies	<p>Experience of support administration, challenges of COVID-19 were presented and future plans were shared during this event, organised by the National Paying Agency, Lithuania (NPA). further improvement of the monitoring system, introduction of new, advanced technologies, etc.</p>
ITC	5/10/2021	Thematic cluster meeting: Food and health sustainability	<p>The workshop organised by the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) aimed to further discuss and validate the usability of project outputs published in the Evaluation Knowledge Bank mainly enhancing the sections 'Relevance for M&E of the CAP' on feedback from stakeholders. Additionally, participants discussed the transferability of project outputs to Member States which have not been involved in testing respective project outputs so far. Cross-fertilisation is based on collaboration with DEMETER, NIVA, SALSA, FACEPA and ENVISION.</p>
OCS	16/10/2021	17th traditional international event BIOFEST	<p>Organic Control System participated on 6 and 7 of October in Subotica at the 17th traditional international event, which contained two segments - an exhibition of organic products and an international conference. Within the topic "Building cooperation and pooling knowledge and resources to the development of organic production in the region", Nenad Novaković presented the Envision H2020 project emphasizing</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			the green effect of the project through continuous monitoring of agricultural land, shifting the focus from limited monitoring of certain fields and dates (time ranges) to monitoring larger territories, throughout the year, emphasizing that with the help of satellite image processing, it will enable systematic monitoring of agricultural practices by promoting agriculture. It was emphasized that the project significantly supports several key pillars of the Green Agenda - sustainable agriculture and biodiversity.
DRXS	23/11/2021	Meeting with UK Paying Agency DEFRA	The follow-up meeting was organised after the Kick-off event, after the Paying agency from the UK shown interest to learn more about possible use and collaboration with the ENVISION project.
LEAF	15/12/2021	R B Organic	LEAF Marque and R B Organic had an initial meeting on the 15th December 2021 to discuss the ENVISION request to host the trial audit. They showed interest in the pitch and were keen to know the benefits for them for hosting the trial audit.
ITC	18/1/2022	AB Kick-off meeting	<p>The overall goal of the meeting was to get to know each other, present ENVISION tangible outcomes and plans (ENVISION platform, services, ...), and agree upon possible future collaboration.</p> <p>The meeting agenda was the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Round table of introductions by the AB members and ENVISION consortium • Introduction of the ENVISION project and what we have done up-to-now • Presentation of the services (AgroApps, NOA, EV ILVO) • Other (feedback, AB involvement, collaboration possibilities and opportunities)

3 Engagement monitoring

To successfully implement communication and Dissemination activities and fulfil the relevant objectives, systematic monitoring is being carried out throughout the project implementation.

ENVISION DC Toolbox is used to monitor implementation and measure the effects of the communication. It is stored on Dropbox, and also all evidence in specific directories and subdirectories. ENVISION DC Toolbox is based on excel spreadsheets that are always up-to-date and show the current situation.

ENVISION activities are monitored **every last day of the month** to see the progress of page visitors and page views, followers, subscribes and posts on social networks.

Figure 28: Project Timeplan

Figure 29: WP7 Timeplan

3.1 Website measurements

Website traffic is monitored using Google Analytics and WP Statistics. Data are collected monthly and provide information on users and their interactions with the site. For a better overview, the data are entered in the table.

Table 8: Number of visitors and page views

C1: Number of visits to the project website		
Date	Visitors	Page Views
29.1.2021	116	9
28.2.2021	204	373
31.3.2021	227	374
30.4.2021	161	291
31.5.2021	184	379
30.6.2021	204	413
31.7.2021	327	273
31.8.2021	626	376
30.9.2021	350	289
31.10.2021	777	1315
30.11.2021	903	1589
31.12.2021	958	1572
31.1.2022	1539	2849
Total	6576	10102

Figure 30: Example of WP Statistics for January 2022

3.2 Social media analytics

Followers and posts are collected monthly for each social channel. The table below shows that the number of followers is increasing every month. The campaign for the subscribers on Slideshare will be started.

Table 9: Followers/subscribers on the social channel

C3: Followers/subscribers on social networks					
Date	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	SlideShare	YouTube
30.9.2020	79	28	35		
31.10.2020	114	43	55		
31.11.2020	128	44	58		
31.12.2020	133	46	59		
29.1.2021	190	49	65		
28.2.2021	217	66	68		
31.3.2021	238	76	73		
30.4.2021	249	87	80		
31.5.2021	262	89	81		
30.6.2021	277	102	82		
31.7.2021	296	115	84		
31.8.2021	300	118	86		
30.9.2021	308	125	89		3
31.10.2021	322	130	94		6
30.11.2021	333	143	101		12
31.12.2021	354	144	104		15
31.1.2022	431	148	125	0	15

Table 10: Number of posts on social channels

C3: Posts on social networks				
Year	Month	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook
2020	September	16	8	3
	October	22	0	3
	November	6	0	0
	December	8	1	0
2021	January	18	2	1
	February	15	7	4
	March	19	5	6
	April	19	10	5
	May	19	9	6
	June	10	11	5
	July	12	3	2
	August	8	1	2
	September	9	9	4

	October	8	5	2
	November	15	4	5
	December	7	5	4
2022	January	14	10	5
	Total:	225	90	57

An entire repetitive campaign is running through the project’s social media to increase their number to reach more followers and subscribers.

Figure 31: Campaign Let's keep in touch!

3.2.1 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account is one of the essential social media tools of the ENVISION communication strategy. At the end of January, the ENVISION LinkedIn account counted 431 followers. Two hundred twenty-five posts were published.

Figure 32: LinkedIn new followers

Figure 33: LinkedIn Impressions

3.2.2 Twitter

The Twitter account had 148 followers and 90 tweets.

Figure 34: Twitter analytics for January 2022

3.2.3 Facebook

The ENVISION Facebook achieved 125 followers and published 57 posts from the beginning of the project.

Figure 35: Facebook followers numbers

Figure 36: Facebook page likes

Figure 37: Post reach

All Posts Published							Ustvari objavo	
■ Doseg: Organski / Plačan ■ Klikov na objavo ■ Odzivi, komentarji in delitve								
Objavljeno	Objavi	Vrsta	Ciljanje	Doseg	Dejavnost	Promote		
11.2.2022 10:12	The recording and presentations available! The			63	10 8		Promoviraj objavo	
9.2.2022 13:36	Thanks to all of you, dear speakers and nearly 300			143	8 17		Promoviraj objavo	
9.2.2022 08:12	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and			78	1 8		Promoviraj objavo	
2.2.2022 12:11	Haven't you registered yet? We are a week before the			67	3 7		Promoviraj objavo	
26.1.2022 18:54	Two weeks are remaining to the event "Earth Observation			305	5 21		Promoviraj objavo	
17.1.2022 11:38	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and			3K	52 36		Promoviraj objavo	
16.1.2022 09:54	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and			1,2K	48 53		Promoviraj objavo	
14.1.2022 12:52	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and			191	7 8		Promoviraj objavo	
11.1.2022 12:04	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and			229	12 23		Promoviraj objavo	
24.12.2021 07:14	The Envision H2020 team wishes you happy holidays!			44	0 6		Promoviraj objavo	
22.12.2021 09:22	Registration is open https://us06web.zoom.us/webin			243	14 18		Promoviraj objavo	
17.12.2021 12:10	Coverage a Jason Tsardanidis from the Envision H2020 project partner			605	33 51		Promoviraj objavo	

Figure 38: Facebook posts examples

3.2.4 YouTube

YouTube channel presents a huge potential to reach various stakeholders. YouTube analytics provide valuable information on views and engagements. So far, the channel has 329 views of videos.

Vsebina kanala

Videosposnetki V živo

Filter

<input type="checkbox"/>	Videoposnetek	Vidnost	Omejilive	Datum ↓	Ogledi	Komentarji	Všečki (in nevshečki)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agric... This Clustering event organized by European projects ENVISION, NIVA, e-shape, DIONE, BEACON and EO-WIDGET had showcased a wide range of...	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	11. feb. 2022 Objavljen	96	0	100,0 % 1 všeček
<input type="checkbox"/>	Deep Learning for Event Detection on Grasslands Jason Tsaridanidis from the National Observatory of Athens and Beyond Centre for EO Research & Satellite Remote Sensing presents grassland...	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	17. dec. 2021 Objavljen	98	0	100,0 % 8 všečkov
<input type="checkbox"/>	ENVISION introduction video Dodajte opis	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	27. sep. 2021 Objavljen	106	0	100,0 % 2 všečka
<input type="checkbox"/>	ENVISION project partner NOAA_work Dodajte opis	Javen	Avtorske pravice in še 1	15. jul. 2021 Objavljen	6	0	-
<input type="checkbox"/>	URDG Team ENVISION WP2 Dodajte opis	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	12. jul. 2021 Objavljen	21	0	-
<input type="checkbox"/>	BEYOND Centre of the National Observatory of Athens provides support ... Dodajte opis	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	30. jun. 2021 Objavljen	1	0	-
<input type="checkbox"/>	RECAP the platform RECAP H2020 Project	Javen	Namenjeno otrokom	30. jun. 2021 Objavljen	1	0	-

Figure 39: Youtube analytics

3.3 ENVISION e-Newsletter analytics

ENVISION audience has 67 subscribers to the e-Newsletters.

ENVISION Newsletter #1

Switch report ▾

Overview Activity ▾ Click Performance Content Optimizer Social E-commerce Inbox Analytics360

40 Recipients

Audience: Envision Delivered: Fri, Feb 26, 2021 6:51 am
 Subject: ENVISION Newsletter #1 [View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

25 Opened	2 Clicked	0 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
---------------------	---------------------	---------------------	--------------------------

Successful deliveries	40 100.0%	Clicks per unique opens	8.0%
Total opens	189	Total clicks	10
Last opened	7/30/21 4:02AM	Last clicked	4/23/21 7:32AM
Forwarded	0	Abuse reports	0

Figure 40: ENVISION Newsletter #1 analytics

ENVISION Newsletter #2

Switch report ▾

Overview Activity ▾ Click Performance Content Optimizer Social E-commerce Inbox Analytics360

50 Recipients

Audience: Envision

Delivered: Mon, Sep 13, 2021 6:12 am

Subject: ENVISION Newsletter #2

[View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

27 Opened	7 Clicked	1 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
--------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Successful deliveries	49 98.0%	Clicks per unique opens	25.9%
Total opens	155	Total clicks	12
Last opened	2/17/22 5:46AM	Last clicked	1/16/22 3:37AM
Forwarded	0	Abuse reports	0

Figure 41: ENVISION Newsletter #2 analytics

To enlarge the pool of the newsletter subscribers, an entire repetitive campaign is running through the project's social media to increase their number.

Figure 42: Newsletter campaign

4 Analysis of results

The table below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which are being used to evaluate the performance of the project's actions. To reach those KPIs, the Consortium is constantly working.

Table 11: Key Performance Indicators

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achived by M 18
C1 Envision website	Numbers of visits to the project website	10.000	6576
C2 A commercial mini-site	A commercial mini-site	1	0
C3 Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, SlideShare)	Followers on Social media	1.200	719
	Posts on social networks relevant to the project	1.200	372
C4 Animation video	Animation video	1	2
C5 ENVISION e-Newsletters	Recipients of project e-newsletters	5.000	50 Mailchimp 504 ENVISION social media 2412 DIH Social Media
C6 ENVISION promotional material	Brochure and leaflets	3.000	1620 printed leaflets
	Roll-up and poster	1 and 1	1 and 1
C7 EuroGEOSS showcase	Expression of interest signed by EuroGEOSS and ENVISION LP	1	0
C8 Hackathon	Hackathon	1	0
C9 Meetings with developers, open-source communities	Meetings with developers, open-source communities	10	6
C10 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	80	14
C11 Policy session	Policy session	1	0
C12 Project events (seminars/workshops)	Project events	8	3
C13 Clustering events/workshops	Clustering events/workshops	2	1
C14 External events	External events	15	10
C15 Presentation/attending at International Conferences	Presentation/attending at International Conferences	20	7
C16 PR articles published in national/regional/European press	PR articles published in national/regional/European press	100	7
C17 Publications in business journals	Publications in business journals	10	1

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achived by M 18
C18 Scientific and Technical publications	Publication	3	0
C19 Podcasts	Podcasts	26	0
C20 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	40	26

5 Conclusions and next steps

According to the Dissemination and communication plan, the goal of the first reporting period was to reach out and raise awareness. Raising awareness is a continuous activity that will be deployed throughout the project's lifespan.

This document defines the intermediate report on dissemination activities and provides a review and analysis of all dissemination and communication tasks in the 18 months of the project. The impact has been very effective: visual and stylistic elements were prepared and used in all ENVISION communication tools. The promotional material was developed: templates, project leaflet, roll up and poster. The website and social media accounts were opened. Two ENVISION Newsletters were issued, and the third one is in progress.

The Kick-off event Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies and the ENVISION Advisory Board Kick-off meeting was organised.

During the second phase (M19 – M34), the aim is to create more target awareness regarding techniques towards researchers, industry key players and stakeholders, relevant industry associations and local communities, and engage farmers who will provide data.

Short term planning:

- Focused publications,
- 3rd, 4th and 5th e-newsletters,
- Press releases,
- Animation video,
- Social media posts,
- Personal interactions,
- Conferences,
- Workshops,
- Events.

Other important activities, such as website updates and participation in webinars, meetings, events, are essential actions for the ENVISION project. In the second phase of the project, the ENVISION project will have more concrete results, so the promotional activities will be more results-oriented.

End of Document

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